

Analysis of morphotectonic and morphometric indicators in the Mauran Valley Basin in Erbil Governorate

Ahmed Abdul Sattar Al-Athari

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 28, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: July 16, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Mauran, Morphotectonic, Morphometri</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5110429</p>	<p><i>The research aims to study the morphotectonic and morphometric indicators (quantitative analysis) of the Mauran Valley Basin in northern Iraq within the Erbil Governorate and the effects of these indicators on the processes and landforms by adopting the study of the natural characteristics of the area (geology, terrain, slope and climate as well as soil and natural vegetation) and analyzing the relationship between them, to contribute to building a building Plans to preserve and develop the environment of the region, and among the most important results of data derived from remote sensing and digital elevation model (DEM) and the use of geographic information systems (GIS), and the adoption of morphotectonic indicators, it became clear that the basin is highly active, affected by its location (within the folds range), as for morphometric, It was found that the flat area of the basin is (474.2) km² and it is ranked seventh, and the rate of bifurcation in it is high (4.4) due to the high number of mattresses (5351), and the high drainage density, which contributed to increasing the chances of erosion and sedimentation, and the rectangular shape of the basin affected by folds and the general slope of the basin and the region.</i></p>

Introduction

The study of any appearance on the surface of the Earth is intended to gather as much information as possible, in order to discover the age, origin, and form as well as the development stages.

Because of the specific geologic features, as well as all the natural factors listed above, the morphotectonic and morphometric characteristics of the Mauran Valley Basin are strongly linked to the hydrologic responses, processes, landforms, and sedimentation amounts in the Basin. Empirical equations and formulas were applied. Different equations and variables were extracted and classified based on the morphometric measurements that were used to determine the morphometric and morphometric indicators of the basin.

Problem statement

The main problem of the subject can be adopted (the natural factors of the study area represented in the geological structure, surface, climate, water resources and natural vegetation affect the morphotectonic and morphometric indicators in the study area) and from this aspect we can present the sub-problems:

- 1- Is the region exposed to tectonic revitalization and what are the most important natural characteristics of the region?
- 2- What are the main indicators that can be adopted in studying the tectonic revitalization of the region?
- 3- What are the morphometric indicators of the study area?
- 4- Is it possible to study morphometric and morphometric indicators using remote sensing and geographic information systems (GIS-RS)

Study hypothesis

The main hypothesis of the topic can be adopted by analyzing the morphometric and morphometric indicators of the basin, it was found that it is affected by the natural characteristics of the study area as well as the geomorphological processes in the study area. From here, secondary hypotheses can be made, including:

- 1- The natural characteristics of the area (geology, topography, climate, and soil) constitute an entry point for the formation of surface features, morphotectonic and morphometric processes and contribute to tectonic activation.
- 2- There are many morphotectonic indicators that can be adopted in the study of water basins
- 3- The nature of the area affected the morphometric indicators of the Mauran Basin
- 4- Through the environment of (GIS and RS) it was possible to study and analyze the morphotectonic and morphometric indicators.

Importance of studying

The research aims to achieve the following:

- 1- Indicate whether there is tectonic activation in the study area
- 2- Analysis of the characteristics of the natural area and its relationship to activation in the study area

3- Quantitative statistical analysis of tectonic activation and basin characteristics (areal, morphological, numerical, and topographical)

Study area location

The Mauran Valley Basin is located in the Erbil Governorate, Shaqlawa District. It is bordered on the north by the estuary of the Little Zab River, on the west by Mount Bermam, on the south by Mount Safin and Mount Surk, and on the east and southeast by Mount KlawQasim and Mount HarirSablik. Astronomically between the arcs of length (44.20.40-44.31). 20) east, and between two latitudes (36.18.40° - 36.36.40°) north map (1). The total area of the Mauran Basin is (474.2 km²).

Figure (1) The location of the Mauran Valley Basin

Geology of the area

The study area is notable for the diversity of its geological formations and the length of the folds in it, as the folds take the general direction from the northwest to the southeast, and the rock discoveries vary through the sedimentation environment, the different rocky components, and the degree of density. Between the second Mesozoic period and the fourth geological period (Quaternary).

Figure (2) rock discoveries in the Mauran Basin.

Formation	Area	Percentage
Balambo	34.8	7.3
Shiranch	67.2	14.2
Anjanh	30.0	6.3
Bellasby	39.3	8.3
Jerx	23.2	4.9
aperture	104.3	22.0
ByeHasan	26.9	5.7
Muqdadiya	15.6	3.3
kolosh	132.9	28.0

Table (1) rock discoveries

Source: General Establishment for Geological Survey and Mining, 1:100000 scale map, prepared by: VarujanKhajikSesakian, Baghdad, 2000, using Arc GIS 9.3

Basin topography and slope

The basin's location revealed that the terrain varied in height and area from the headwaters (the water division line) to the mouth on the Little Zab River northwest of the basin. 3), (4) and Table (2) indicate that four terrain features may be predicted:

- 1- The undulating region covering the northern parts (the mouth of the basin) is the confluence of the large tributary, with an area.

54.5 km² and a rate of 11.5% 2- Low hills cover most of the area around the estuary and the center of the region and 132.7 km² and a percentage of 28% 3- As for the high hills only covered an area of 151.8 km² and a percentage of 32% and occupy most of the central and southern regions of the basin 4- As for the mountains, they were ranked third In terms of area along the basin from the center to the southwest and east with an area of 135.2 and a rate of 28.5%.

Table (2) Formation areas

Formation	Name	Area	Percentage
373 - 600	wavy	54.5	11.5

600.1 - 800	low hills	132.7	28
800.1 - 1000	high hills	151.8	32
1000.1 - 1971	mountains	135.2	28.5

Source: Figure 3

As for the normality of the regression in the study area, and through the analysis of maps (5) and (6) and tables (3) and (4), it becomes clear to us:

- According to (Zink) classification, the region represents five categories of slope degrees, represented by (flat lands) with the lowest (0-1.9) degrees, and it represents the areas of valley stomachs, estuaries, and floodplains, with the least area (10 km²) and a rate of 2.1%.
- As for the degree of gradient, the areas of severe erosion (30 and more) occupied a degree in the south and southeast of the basin (highly cut) with an area of (16.7 km²).
- The category (8-15.9) degrees (undulating lands) recorded the highest area with 188.2 km² and a percentage of (39.7%)
- As for the slope direction in the region, the highest trend was recorded in the (northeast) at 18.45 with an area of (87.5 km²), followed by the southwest direction with 17.12 with an area (81.2 km²), which is in line with the slope direction of the basin (valleys), folds and faults.

Table (3) Zink classification for regression

Degree	Name	Area	Percentage
0 – 1.9	flat	10	2.1
2 – 7.9	slight ripple	145.8	30.7
8 – 15.9	crispy	188.2	39.7
16 – 29.9	diced	113.5	23.9
30 and over	cut high	16.7	3.5

Figure (4) lines of equal height

Figure (6) The direction of the gradient in the Mauran Basin

Figure (3) Topography of the basin

Figure (5) Zink classification for regression

Source: - From the researcher's work using the Digital Elevation Model (DEM) and the program (ArcGIS, 10.3).

Table (4) areas of the regression direction

Directions	Areas	Percentage
straight or no direction	0.17	0.04
north	39.02	8.23
Northeast	87.45	18.45
east	48.51	10.23
Southeast	34.23	7.22
South	44.21	9.33
Southwest	81.18	17.12
West	57.69	12.17
North West	51.59	10.88
north	30.05	6.34

Source: Figure (8)

The climate of the study area is similar to that of Iraq with high values of solar radiation (41.47) joules / m² / day in June, maximum temperatures (45.87) m in July, rain being interrupted, lack of humidity, and a rise in wind speed (3.1) m/s in the summer, August, and the occurrence of rain precipitation (97.09) mm mm in the month of March, which accompanies a decrease The values of solar radiation, temperatures and low wind speed in the cold season (winter)

Table (5) Monthly averages of climatic elements in Shaqlawa station for the period 2010-2019

Month	Rainfall	Solar radiation	Wind speed	Humidity	Min.T	Max.T	Stan.T
JAN	63.27	17.47	2.81	70.62	-9.99	17.98	3.01
FEB	73.09	22.61	2.53	67.05	-9.7	20.25	4.92
MAR	97.09	29.33	2.23	64.77	-7.82	25.43	8.71
APR	93.36	35.62	1.51	58.03	-2.92	30.79	14.33
MAY	73.63	39.83	1.27	47.34	6.87	36.68	20.63
JUN	8.72	41.47	1.71	27.8	11.37	43.51	27.38
JUL	0	40.48	2.5	19.14	14.85	45.86	31.39
AUG	0.54	36.95	3.11	19.79	17.03	44.69	31.04
SEP	11	31.36	2.84	23.93	10.47	41.03	26.05
OCT	49.54	24.67	3.01	39.91	2.94	35.15	18.63
NOV	42.09	18.76	2.89	53.71	-3.06	26.74	10.18
DEC	92.27	15.9	2.84	66.32	-7.87	26.09	5.03

<https://power.larc.nasa.gov/data-access-viewer>

Soil

Soil is a geomorphological factor that determines the strength and volume of water drainage for river floods, and this role appears through the direct relationship between soil permeability on the one hand, and the volume of water flow in the river network on the other hand. They are as follows:

- **Medium and shallow fish soil:**

The soil occupies the northern part and the center of the region, and occupies an area of 247.8 km² and is 52% of the study area. These areas are characterized as bad land. The cracked rocks in this soil consist of compactions and mudstone with layers of sandy and alluvial rocks in the Bay Hassan Formation. It is a (brown) soil whose thickness decreases in the highlands areas, especially at the peaks, and increases in thickness at the feet of the highlands (Imad Al-din Omar Hassan, 1998.)

- **Rugged and cracked mountainous soil:**

It covers a wide area of the study area 216.5 km² and 45.6% in the center and south of the Mauran Basin area. Map (7). It is characterized by its shallowness due to the steepness of the slope. It is derived from limestone and metamorphic rocks. Its surface shows the effects of severe water erosion and snow, its chestnut color and texture Rough, and it is not suitable for agriculture because of its ruggedness and steep slope. As they vary in their slopes, they are shallow in slopes and deep in valleys, and because of the high rates of slope that exceed (30) and some of them reach (90) and very fast surface runoff in which water erosion processes prevail, which is related to many morphometric variables.

- **Lithosol soil with lime:**

It appears in a limited way in the northern part, with an area of 10 km² and a percentage of 2.1 of the basin area. It is a shallow, shallow rocky soil that is not suitable for agriculture due to its constant exposure to erosion

Figure (7) Soil of the Mauran Basin

Figure (8) Index (NDVI)

Vegetation index in the Mauran Basin

From the analysis of Figure (8), two types of vegetative cover can be distinguished by adopting the (Ndvi) index for a visual that was taken on 1-3-2021. They are the light cover spread with a percentage of (64.3%) represented by the weeds and scattered plants spread in the steepest and sandy areas with soils Few fish in the center and south of the basin, and the cover is medium density (35.7%) and is represented by forests and agricultural lands in the north of the basin and the northwest at the downstream region.

Morphotectonic Indicators in the Mauran Basin

One of the methods of studying land forms that are subjected to deformation due to tectonic and structural activity Morphometric (quantitative) indicators with geomorphological significance have been adopted to determine the effectiveness of tectonic activity, through which it shows the role of structural distortions in the formation of geomorphological units, and indicates the occurrence of tectonic activation, which contributes to the acceleration of geomorphological processes of erosion and sedimentation as well as morpho-dynamic morpho-tectonic processes, and the topic can be studied through Several indicators are:

Topographic Symmetry Factor.: Topographic Symmetry Factor

The index of the topographic symmetry factor (T) represents the extent of the displacement of the main course of the water basin from the basin axis, and the coefficient values are represented by ranges from (0-1), which reflects a complete or relatively zigzag asymmetry. Symmetry and whenever it goes towards (1) it tends towards asymmetry (displacement), which shows the state of being affected by the zigzag of the bottom layer (subsurface) or its faulting, which leads to the displacement of the main course of the basin with the direction of the subsurface faults, and the types of geomorphological index (T) are represented by the rise if The value was (<0.6), moderate if the value was (0.6-0.3), characterized by low if the value was (>0.3), and the (T) index is expressed by applying the equation: (Burbank, DW, & Anderson, RS2001)

$$T = Da/Dd$$

Where: T = index and terrain symmetry factor T.

Da = the distance from the midline of the basin to the midline of the main tortuous stream of the basin.

Dd = the distance from the midline of the pelvis to the outer boundary line at the midline.

By applying the equation, the index value reached (T) (0.5), which is a moderate value indicating the equivalence of the topographic symmetry and unzigzag. Figure (9) and Table (8)

Asymmetry Factor: (AF)

The asymmetry factor (AF) measures the slope of the sides of the basin relative to the main course in the water basin, which resulted from its influence by tectonic forces, and the AF index values were classified as high if the value was (<65), and moderate if the value was (65-57). , and low if it is (> 57), and the (AF) index can be expressed by the equation: (2002, Keller, EA and Pinter, N)

$$AF = 100(AR/AT)$$

Where: AF=asymmetry factor index.

AR = downstream of the basin area on the right side of the main stream.

AT = total area of the pelvis. When applying the equation, the indicator value (AF) reached (66.7), which is a high value, and it is a value that indicates a side slope as a result of tectonic activation. Table (9) and Figure (10)

Figure (10) Asymmetry Index

Figure (9) terrain symmetry index and factor

Source: - From the researcher's work using the Digital Elevation Model (DEM) and the program (ArcGIS, 10.3)

Stream Length- Gradient Index: (SL):

Hard rocks that are resistant to erosion processes, while the low values of the index characterize low tectonic activity and reflect the presence of brittle rocks that are less resistant to erosion processes. And the third value (>300) has a low value and the index value can be calculated by applying the equation (2002, Keller, EA and Pinter, N)

$$SL = (\Delta H / \Delta L) L$$

Where: L = the total length of the valley.

ΔH = height difference in the specified downstream region.

ΔL is the length of the straight line in the specified downstream region.

The (SL) index represents the calculation of the lengths of the stream, and the (SL) index is used to assess the resistance of rocks to erosion processes (water erosion) and its relationship to the activities of tectonic activities, and this indicator is affected by the degree of slope

The meandering of the river valley channel is also related to the strength of the flow, as the strength of the flow shows the length or shortness of the drainage channel, and the ability of the flow is related to erosion, erosion and sediment transfer (& Pete, 2014 Carolina Doranti-Tiritan). Index (SL) (312.4), which is a value of moderate activity, which indicates moderate tectonic activity and the presence of erosion-resistant rocks (Table 10) Figure (11).

Ratio Of Valley Floor Width To Valley Height:(VF)

The (VF) index reflects the difference between the valley floor that was formed in response to an increase in the rate of tectonic activation of the base rocks (the subsurface layer), and the valley floor that was formed due to lateral erosion of the valleys sloping down the hills, which reflects low tectonic activity. The sources of the basin are characterized by depression, which reflects high tectonics, and the index values gradually increase as we head towards the downstream region, which is characterized by low tectonics, and the index values vary according to the drainage energy and the hardness of the base rocks (Verrios., Zygouri., and Kokkalas, 2004, 1708) classified as high For the value (>0.5), moderate for the value (1-0.5) and low if the value is (1<), and it can be extracted by the equation ((BULL, WB MCFADDEN1977.L.

$$VF = 2V_{fw} / [(E_{ld} - E_{sc}) + (E_{rd} - E_{sc})]$$

Where: V_{fw} = width of the valley floor.

E_{ld} = height of the left valley section.

E_{rd} = height of the right section of the valley.

E_{sc} = valley floor height.

When applying the equation to the Mauran Basin, the indicator value reached (2.1), which is a low value, and it can be inferred from this value that the Mauran Basin has low tectonic activity, and this confirms the length of the course and its slope in the basin. Table (11) and Figure (12)

Figure (12) The ratio of the width of the valley floor to the height of the valley

Figure (11) Indicator of the length of the stream and the degree of its slope

Source: - By researcher’s work using the Digital Elevation Model (DEM) and the program (ArcGIS, 10.3).

Mountain front slalom indicator smf

The (smf) index reflects the balance between erosion and the tectonic forces forming the mountain front, and the mountain front index can be calculated through the equation (Bull and McFadden 1977).

$$Smf=Lmf/Ls$$

-Lmf= the length of the mountain front sinuosity.

The length of the front of the mountain is zigzag.

-Ls= the straight-line length of the mountain front

The length of the straight line of the mountain front.

If the values of the SMF index are less than (1.6), they indicate active tectonic processes (erosion, roughness and zigzag at the front of the mountain (and if the index values exceed the mentioned number, they indicate less or relatively low tectonic processes, from Table (13) and Fig. 13) Which shows the indicators of the basin, it is clear that it is of high activity, and the types of the indicator are represented according to classification in Table (12) as follows:

Final Classification of Tectonic Indicators (LAT):

The final classification (LAT) represents the compilation of the results of the values and classifications of geomorphological indicators and all the results of applying the previous equations, the criteria adopted in the classification (VF), (SL), (T), (AF), (SMF) with giving each variable three classifications (1) High, (2) Moderate, (3) Low, as it will lead to giving a comprehensive view of the impact of these geomorphological indicators on tectonic activities in the Mauran Basin if the study relies on four degrees for the first classification, which is very high, as the value of this indicator is between (1- 1.5), the second is high, with its value (2-1.5), the third is moderate, as the value of this indicator is more than (2-2.5), and the fourth is low if it is recorded (more than 2.5) Table (15), which represented the tectonic classifications in four categories (2013, 2013, Ziyad Elias)

By compiling the results of the equation classes for all the indicators applied to the study area, it became clear that the (LAT) value is (2), meaning that it is within the class (2) with the tectonic classification value (2.5-2), which represents moderate to high tectonic activities and this applies to the region Study table (14).

Table (8) LAT Relative Tectonic Activity Index

Indications	SI	Vf	T	Smf	Af	s/n	Lat	Item	Degree
Basin	2	3	2	1	1	9	1.2	1	High activity

Source: - By researcher’s work using the Digital Elevation Model (DEM) and the program (arccgis, 10.3).

Morphometric features in the Mauran Basin:

By looking at Table (16) that shows the results of the morphometric analysis of the digital height model with an accuracy of distinction (30) m, and based on the morphometric toolbox v.2 developed by (2015 Beg) published on the American ESRI website, and it is a complementary method For morphometric measurements (ArcGIS – Hydrology) toolbox), and on this basis, the basin was studied based on two digital height models (30) m and on the basis of calculating

The following morphometric parameters (drainage network, morphological characteristics, histological characteristics, and topographical characteristics, as well as the Hypsometric analysis).

Drainage Network Parameters

The characteristics of the natural area, including the characteristics of the rocks, their structural shapes, the degree of their response to the old and current climatic influences, (permeability, porosity and hardness), and the general slope of the surface, as well as the structures of cracks, joints and folds, affect the general shape of the basin tributaries with different levels of numbers and lengths (calculated 2001) and among the important parameters in the exchange network

Numbers and lengths of Stream Order

And in a method (Horton, 1945) and modified by) Schumms1956 (1952 Strahler), which states that the first rank that no tributary flows into, and the second that consists of the confluence of two tributaries from the first, and this indicates that the area is damaged if the number of river ranks increases and In contrast to him, the area becomes in the stage of maturity, i.e. (exposed to erosion more than others) and from Table (16) and Figure (14) it appears to us that the basin is of the seventh rank and the basin record (5351) valley for all ranks and (4049) the first rank is the most numerous in the basin is It agrees with Horton's laws, and this indicates the activity of the erosion geomorphological processes that formed the area, especially the water (surface), as the large numbers indicate the spur of the basin and vice versa that the area has lost part of its terrain by erosion, as the basin recorded the total lengths of all ranks (1856.1) km, and this It means that the basin in which the lengths of the mattresses are few means that it runs in an arcuate area.

Figure (14) River Mattresses of Mauran Basin

Figure (13) Smf . mountain front zigzag indicator

Source: - By researcher's work using the Digital Elevation Model (DEM) and the program (ArcGIS, 10.3).

Table (16) Morphometric coefficients (areal, numerical, morphological and topographic) for the Mauran Valley Basin

1.	morphometric analysis	Maoran
2.	Drainage Network Parameters	
3.	Number of stream order 1	4049
4.	Number of stream order 2	1007
5.	Number of stream order 3	236
6.	Number of stream order 4	45
7.	Number of stream order 5	11
8.	Number of stream order 6	2
9.	Number of stream order 7	1
10.	Total no. of stream order	5351
11.	Length of stream order 1 km	924.9
12.	Length of stream order 2 km	486.8
13.	Length of stream order 3 km	241.6
14.	Length of stream order 4 km	103.6
15.	Length of stream order 5 km	20.9
16.	Length of stream order 6 km	60.6
17.	Length of stream order 7 km	17.7
18.	Total length of streams km	1856.1
19.	Rb for 1:2	4
20.	Rb for 2:3	4.3
21.	Rb for 3:4	5.2
22.	Rb for 4:5	4.1
23.	Rb for 5:6	5.5
24.	Rb for 6:7	2
25.	Average Bifurcation ratio	4.2
26.	Geometry Parameters	
27.	Total Basin Area(Kms ²)	474.2
28.	Total Basin Surface Area(Kms ²)	493.2
29.	Total Basin perimeter(Kms)	135.1

30.	Basin Length (Kms)	52.7
31.	Main Channel Length (Kms)	65.5
32.	ideal channel length(Kms)	45.7
33.	Form factor	0.2
34.	Rotundity coefficient	4.6
35.	Drainage Texture	39.6
36.	Elongation ratio	0.46
37.	Drainage Texture Analysis	
38.	Drainage density (km/km ²)	3.9
39.	Stream frequency (number/km ²)	11.3
40.	Infiltration Number	44.1
41.	Drainage Intensity	2.9
42.	Basin Relief	
43.	Height of Basin outlet (m)	373
44.	Maximum Height of basin(m)	1971
45.	Total Basin Relief (H) m	1598
46.	Relief Ratio	30.3
47.	Relative Relief Ratio	1.18
48.	Ruggedness Number	6.23
49.	Melton Ruggedness Number	6.74
50.	Terrain Undulation Index	
51.	Hypsometric Integral (Height Area Ratios)	0.30

Source: By researcher's work based on 1- (SRTM - 1 arc second (30 meters) and ArcGIS - Morphometric toolbox V.2

- **Rotundity coefficient R_c**: Extract from the equation: (Zavoianu1985, Strahler1964): $A_c = (R_c \cdot L_b^2 \times (\pi/4A))$, where A is the area of the basin and L_b is the length of the basin, and it is closer to the circular or semi-circular as the product approaches From the correct one, and if its value rises to 1.27, then it is a square, but if it reaches (10-15) it is a rectangle, and from the table (16) we find that the Mauran Basin recorded (4.6), and this indicates the rectangular shape, reducing the risk of flooding in the area to reach The water is in the form of waves, unlike the circular shape, which reaches its waves at once and in a relatively short period.

- **Drainage texture (Dt Drainage Texture)**: (Horton1945) is the sum of the numbers of riverine ranks to the basin circumference, $Dt = Nu/P$, where t D Drainage texture, Nu numbers of riverine ranks, P the perimeter of the basin, was classified (Smith 1950) into five classes It depends on the nature of the area, especially (rocks, climate, slope, vegetation, and soil type), ranging from very coarse (less than 2), coarse (2-4), moderate (4-6) and very soft more than (8). It was noted that the Mauran Basin recorded (39.6). Thus, the basin is very soft, and this can be attributed to the cracks and structures, the lack of resistance of the rocks, the weak vegetation cover and the increase in the slope in the area.

Elongation Ratio Re: (Schumm, 1956) to determine the elongation of the pelvis or its approach to the rectangular shape or its distance from it, by dividing the length of the diameter of a circle whose area is equal to the area of the pelvis to the maximum length of the basin, and according to (Pareta and Pareta, 2011) it can be classified The elongation of the pelvis is between (0-1), if it is (0-0.5) very elongated, (0.5-0.7) long, (0.7-0.8) short, (0.8-0.9) oval, (0.9-1) round, and from a table (16) We note that the elongation ratio was in Mauran (0.46), and it is extracted from the equation proposed by (Zavoianu, 1985): $Re = 1.129 \times \sqrt{A} / L_b$, where Re is the rate of elongation, L_b is the length of the basin, A is the area, 1.129 is a constant and is inferred from it The basin is very elongated due to its association with the slope and direction of the folds in the area, thus the low risk of flooding and the increase in water losses, and it is identical with the rest of the formal parameters that indicate the basin's departure from the regular circular shape.

Drainage Texture Analysis, which includes the following:

- **Drainage Density D_d**, according to (Horton, 1945) is calculated by dividing the lengths of the waterways of the total basin by the area of the basin $D_d = L_u/A$, A represents the area of the drainage basin, L_u is the length of the total streams of the drainage network, which is an indicator of the characteristics of the drainage network. The area of (soil permeability, slope, climate quality and natural vegetation) that control this density and its variation from one region to another, and the high density indicates the risks of flooding, while the high permeability, lack of precipitation and lack of slope increase the coefficient of infiltration and lack of surface runoff. In the WadiMauran Basin and from Table (16) it was recorded (3.9) km / km² and this indicates that the natural characteristics of the area and the increase in lengths in relation to the area of the basins, and consequently, the increase in run-off, increase in erosion and the sedimentary output of the basins of the area.

- **River frequency (F Stream frequency)**, which is the relationship between the number of river ranks and the area (calculated, 2001) $A / F = Nu$, where F is the river frequency, A is the area and Nu is the total number of

ranks, and it shows the nature of the region in terms of geological structure, vegetation cover and the extent of soil permeability. In addition to the rain intensity and the amount of rain falling on the area, and in the basin, the river frequency (numerical density) was recorded (11.3) streams / km² in Mauran, and with these data, the area is medium to high in numerical and longitudinal density depending on the type of climate, gypsum and limestone rocks as well as the slope of the area.

- **Infiltration Number Ifn**) according to (Satish and Vajrappa 2014) and its equation: $I_{fn} = F \times D_d$, I_{fn} , drainage density, F river frequency, i.e. the product of multiplying the drainage density by river frequency, as the higher the number indicates less leakage. The surface runoff rises, and the opposite is true. The Mauran Basin recorded a number of infiltration (44.1), respectively, which is a high value indicating less leakage and increased runoff.

- **Drainage Intensity Di**: This coefficient is related to both the river frequency and the drainage density and represents the ratio between the river frequency to the drainage density (Pareta 2011) $D_i = F/D_d$: where D_i is the intensity of drainage, F is the river frequency, D_d is the drainage density, and through the study it appeared that the Mauran Basin has a drainage intensity of (2.9) and it is considered a moderate intensity and it is related to the river frequency and its drainage density and therefore moderate flow intensity, due to the slope of the region, especially the high areas in the south and southwest, and thus its exposure to rock and soil erosion.

Analysis of the terrain characteristics (Basin Relief): through it it is possible to know the topographic characteristics of the basin and then the degree of gradient and its effects on the water division areas and understanding the development of the water network. As well as understanding the pelvic age stage, the most important of which can be summarized:

- **Height of Basin outlet m**): It represents the lowest height in the basin and often the estuaries of the basins. In the Mauran basin, the digital height model (DEM) was adopted to obtain (the highest and lowest points of height) and it was found that the point (373) m in The mouth of the basin is in the northeast in the Upper Zab River.

Maximum height of basin m: It represents the highest areas around the basin (the water division areas) or the sources of the basin. It was recorded (1971) m at the southern and southeastern parts of the basin.

- **Total Basin Relief H**: It is the difference between the highest and lowest level of the basin and recorded in the Mauran Basin (1598) m, which contributes to the emergence of a direct relationship between the increase in water erosion processes with the rise in the values of the sprocket of the basin and vice versa.

- **Relief Ratio**: According to (Schumm, 1956) $R_{HI} = H/L_b$, R_{HI} for the dentition, H for the molar of the total pelvis, L_b for the length of the pelvis (km). through this ratio it is possible to deduce the life stage of the basin, as the minimum values indicate the activity of erosion processes and retreat towards the source and the progress of the basin in its downstream cycle, and The opposite refers to the molar of the basin and its youth and a delay in its downstream cycle (Abu Raya 2007) and from table (16) the Mauran Basin record (30.3), which is a percentage indicating the progress of the basin in its downstream cycle in general and the activity of erosion processes and the increase in sediment quantities for the molar of the basin.

- **Relative Relief Ratio**: The low values of these ratios indicate the weak resistance of the rocks and the activity of erosion factors in the basin when the climate is stable. It can be obtained by dividing the topography of the basin by its surroundings multiplied by (10) (calculated 2001) or from the following equation $R_{hp} = H * 100/P$ proposed by Melton (1957) where R_{hp} represents the relative terrain, H is the height difference (km), P is the circumference of the basin (km), and this ratio was (11.8), which is a high percentage confirming the activity of erosion processes in the basin due to the severity of the gradient and the intensity of sprockets and rock hardness.

- **Ruggedness Number**: This coefficient shows the relationship between the sprout of the surface of the basin floor and the length of the drainage network in it, i.e. the results of the drainage density with the sprocket of the basin (Al-Dulaimi, 2017). This indicator can be obtained from the equation proposed by (1964 Strahler): $R_n = D_d * (H/1000)$, where R_n is the value of roughness, H is the difference in height between the highest and lowest point in the basin (km), D_d of the drainage density. Record from the table (16) that the number of roughness (6.23) for the basin (Mauran) is high due to the correlation of this coefficient with the density Drainage, which in turn depends on the lengths and numbers of river beds.

The Melton Ruggedness Number is an indicator that shows the erosion of the basin through the hardness of the terrain inside the river basin, and it can be obtained from the equation (Pareta and Pareta 2011) $M_{Rn} = H/A * 0.5$, and the Mauran Basin recorded the number (6.74), which confirms the value of the previous roughness that Refers to high values, meaning the area is rammed and the density of drainage increases. The higher the drainage density and the trough in the basin, the higher the ruggedness coefficient values of the high slope and the increase of erosion and sedimentation and vice versa.

The concentrated watersheds in the Mauran Basin: From Figure (15) it can be seen the places of concentration of water spaces, and according to the elevation model (30) m, the northern and central areas of the basin were the highest areas that absorbed water because of the largest number of valleys, especially the first and second ranks of most of the basins, which The areas that can accommodate water quantities varied in

relation to the characteristics of the surrounding area (morphometric, topographic, geological, climatic and environmental).

- **Basin expansion direction:** through Figure (16) and based on the data of the digital elevation model (DEM) 30 m and from the (Basin Center) tool, it was possible to determine the direction of the basin expansion in the main geographical directions, as the effect of the natural side on limiting the expansion in the southeast and southwest direction due to the presence of folds The convexity represented by the mountains of Jishkeh, Sefin, and Kalwaqasem, and the expansion was limited to the north and northwest towards the estuary, and its direction shifted from northwest to north to flow into the Upper Zab River (the Great) at the Mukardan region. The north-west, which is in the form of a torsion of (10.8) km, as for the other directions, the nature of the gradient of the region from the southeast and south to the north and northwest is a sharpness of expansion in other directions and also the division of water south, southwest and east did not allow for expansion towards it

Figure (16) The direction of expansion of the pelvis

Figure (15) Watersheds in the basin

Source: - By researcher's work using the Digital Elevation Model (DEM) and the program (ArcGIS, 10.3).

Conclusions

- From the morphotectonic indicators of the landforms, it appears that the basin is located in an active tectonic area, in which erosion, sedimentation and increased river drainage occur.

One of the morphometric indicators of the basin is that it is of the seventh rank and is characterized by a rectangular shape affected by the folds surrounding the basin, the general slope direction of the area, and a high rate of bifurcation associated with the quality of the relatively soft rocks represented by limestone and gypsum rocks, and a humid climate in winter.

- Contributed to the intensity of drainage and high river frequency

Hypsometric integration indicates that the pelvis is going through a stage of late maturation and the onset of aging

- Also, the gear indicator indicates that the area has high erosion, especially in the southern and southwestern regions, unlike the northern and northwestern regions.

- The western and northwestern regions (downstream region) also recorded the highest trend in the expansion of the basin due to the lack of erosion in it.

- It was also found that the same area can invest water catchments in it due to the gathering of the main tributaries in it and its proximity to the settlements and the presence of good soil near the outfalls.

Recommendations

Construction of dams in watershed areas

- Implementation of embankments and fences in the steepest areas due to the presence of tectonic activation

Building integrated climate stations in the region

Carrying out future detailed studies on hydrological potentials

Adoption of morphometric and morphometric indicators by using remote sensing techniques and geographic information systems to build geographical models that serve the region and to assess and develop lands

References

- Strahler, A. N. (1964) *Quantitative geomorphology of drainage basin and channel networks*. Handbook of applied hydrology, p.439-476
- Beg, A. A. F. (2015) Morphometric Toolbox: A New Technique in Basin Morphometric Analysis Using ArcGIS (Pages 21-30). *Global Journal of Earth Science and Engineering* 2, 21-30

- BULL, W.B. MCFADDEN, L. TECTONIC GEOMORPHOLOGY NORTH AND SOUTH OF THE GARLOCK FAULT, CALIFORNIA. *Geomorphology in Arid regions*, D.O. Doehring, ed Publications in Geomorphology, State University of New York at Bingamton, 1977, p.116.
- Burring, P, Soil and conditions in Iraq, Explority soil map of Iraq (1) Baghdad, 1960.
- Carolina Doranti-Tiritan, Peter Christian Hackspacher, Daniel Henrique de Souza, Marli Carina Siqueira-Ribeiro, The Use of the Stream Length-Gradient Index in Morphotectonic Analysis of Drainage Basins in Poços de Caldas Plateau, SE Brazil, *International Journal of Geosciences*, vol 22, 2014, P. 1387
- Burbank, D. W., & Anderson, R. *Tectonic Geomorphology*. Blackwell Science, Massachusetts, 2001, P.274.
- Pareta, K. & U. Pareta (2011) *Quantitative morphometric analysis of a watershed of Yamuna basin, India using ASTER (DEM) data and GIS*. *International Journal of Geomatics and Geosciences*, 2, 248-269.
- Pike, R.J & Wilson, S, E; (1971): *Elevation- Relief Ratio, Hypsometric Integral, and Geomorphic Area – Altitude Analysis*, G S A Bulletin, V 82, p 1079
- Satish, K. & H. Vajrappa (2014) *Morphological Parameter Estimation Derived From ASTER DEM Using GIS and Remote Sensing Techniques*. *International Journal of Research*, 1, 1959-1967.
- Schumm, S. A. (1956) *Evolution of drainage systems and slopes in badlands at Perth Amboy*, New Jersey. *Geological society of America bulletin*, 67, 597-646
- Smith, K. G. (1950) *Standards for grading texture of erosional topography*. *American Journal of Science*, 248, 655-668.
- Strahler, A. N. (1952b) *Hypsometric (area-altitude) analysis of erosional topography*. *Geological Society of America Bulletin*, 63, 1117-1142.
- Varoujan K. Sissakian, Faiza A. Ibrahim, 1998, Series of Geological hazard maps of Erbil and Mahabad Quadrangle op.cit, P13.
- Verrios., Zygouri., and Kokkalas, MORPHOTECTONIC ANALYSIS IN THE ELIKI FAULT ZONE (GULF OF CORINTH, GREECE), *Bulletin of the Geological Society of Greece International Congress*, 2004, p.1708.
- Wilson, E. (1990). *Engineering hydrology*. 4th edition, RIBS/ Macmillan
- Yogesh Hole et al 2019 *J. Phys.: Conf. Ser.* 1362 012121
- Zavoianu, I. 1985. *Morphometry of drainage basins*. Elsevier. p100
- ZiyadEliaS, , Quantitative Geomorphology of analyzing tectonic activity in the Roczek and Shwork rivers valley in the Zagros Mountains (Iraqi Kurdistan), *International Journal of Enhanced Research in Science Technology & Engineering*, Vol. 2 Issue 11, November-2013, p25

Author Information

Prof. Dr. Ahmed Abdul Sattar Al-Athari
 University Of Mustansiriyah
 College of Education, Department Of Geography
 Iraq, Baghdad
